

Feature Extractions with Geometric Algebra for Classification of Objects

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Abstract—Most conventional methods of feature extraction do not pay much attention to the geometric properties of data, even in cases where the data have spatial features. In this study we introduce geometric algebra to undertake various kinds of feature extraction from spatial data. Geometric algebra is a generalization of complex numbers and of quaternions, and it is able to describe spatial objects and relations between them. This paper proposes to use geometric algebra to systematically extract geometric features from data given in a vector space. We show the results of classification of hand-written digits, which were classified by feature extraction with the proposed method.

I. INTRODUCTION

Because nowadays, enormous amounts of data are available in various fields, data mining which analyzes data to reveal interesting information becomes more and more necessary. But so far most conventional methods of feature extraction ignore the geometric properties of data even in the case where the data have spatial features. For example, when m vectors are measured from an object in three-dimensional space, conventional methods represent the object by $x \in \mathbb{R}^{3m}$ which is the vector made by arranging m groups of 3 coordinates of each vector in a row. However, because these coordinate values depend on the definition of the coordinate system, inference or classification becomes remarkably bad, when objects are measured in a coordinate system different from the one used for learning. Furthermore, spatial information of the object in three-dimensional space is lost when each element $x \in \mathbb{R}^{3m}$ is, for example, normalized. Some conventional methods may extract coordinate-free features, but whether such features arise and are adopted depends on the experience of the model builder.

In this study, we use geometric algebra (GA) which can describe spatial vectors and higher order subspace relations between them [1],[2],[3], to systematically undertake various kinds of feature extractions, and to improve precision and robustness in classification problems. There are already many successful examples of its use in image processing, signal processing, colored image processing, or multi-dimensional time-series signal processing with complex numbers or quaternions, which are low dimensional GAs [4],[5],[6],[7],[8],[9],[10]. In addition, GA-valued neural network learning methods for learning input-output relationships [11] are well studied.

In our proposed method, geometric features extracted with GA can also be used for learning a data distribution. In this study, we use geometric features to learn a Gaussian mixture

model (GMM) with the expectation maximization (EM) algorithm [12], and apply this to a classification problem. Because each feature extraction derived by the proposed method has its own advantages and disadvantages, we apply a plural mixture of GMMs for the classification problem. As an example of multi-class classification of geometric data, we use a hand-written digit dataset of the UCI Machine Learning Repository [13]. When classifying new hand-written digits in practice with the learning model, it is natural to expect that the coordinate system in a real new environment differs from the one used for obtaining the learning dataset. Therefore, in this paper, we evaluate the classification performance for randomly rotated test data.

II. METHOD

A. Feature extraction with GA

GA is also called Clifford algebra. An orthonormal basis $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{e}_n\}$ can be chosen for a real vector space \mathbb{R}^n . The GA of \mathbb{R}^n , denoted by \mathcal{G}_n , is constructed by an associative and bilinear product of vectors, the geometric product, which is defined by

$$\mathbf{e}_i \mathbf{e}_j = \begin{cases} 1 & (i = j), \\ -\mathbf{e}_j \mathbf{e}_i & (i \neq j). \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

GAs are also defined for negative squares $\mathbf{e}_i^2 = -1$ of some or all basis vectors. Such GAs have many applications in computer graphics, robotics, virtual reality, etc [3]. But for our purposes definition (1) will be sufficient.

Now we consider two vectors $\{\mathbf{a}_l = \sum_i a_{li} \mathbf{e}_i, l = 1, 2\}$ in \mathbb{R}^n . Their geometric product is

$$\mathbf{a}_1 \mathbf{a}_2 = \sum_{i=1}^n a_{1i} a_{2i} + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n (a_{1i} a_{2j} - a_{1j} a_{2i}) \mathbf{e}_{ij}, \quad (2)$$

where the abbreviation $\mathbf{e}_{ij} = \mathbf{e}_i \mathbf{e}_j$ is adopted in the following. The first term is the commutative inner product $\mathbf{a}_1 \cdot \mathbf{a}_2 = \mathbf{a}_2 \cdot \mathbf{a}_1$. The second term is the anti-commutative outer product $\mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \mathbf{a}_2 = -\mathbf{a}_2 \wedge \mathbf{a}_1$. The second term is called a 2-blade. Linear combinations of 2-blades are called bivectors, expressed by $\sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}_2} w_I \mathbf{e}_I, w_I \in \mathbb{R}$, where $\mathcal{I}_2 = \{i_1 i_2 \mid 1 \leq i_1 < i_2 \leq n\}$ is the ordered combination set of two different elements from $\{1, \dots, n\}$. For parallel vectors $\mathbf{a}_1 = \kappa \mathbf{a}_2, \kappa \in \mathbb{R}$, and the second term becomes 0.

Next, we consider the geometric product of $\mathbf{a}_1 \mathbf{a}_2 = \mathbf{a}_2 \cdot \mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2 \wedge \mathbf{a}_1$ with a third vector \mathbf{a}_3 . First, because $\mathbf{a}_1 \cdot \mathbf{a}_2 \in \mathbb{R}$, $(\mathbf{a}_1 \cdot \mathbf{a}_2) \mathbf{a}_3$ is a vector. Next, $(\mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \mathbf{a}_2) \mathbf{a}_3 =$

$(\sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}_2} w_I \mathbf{e}_I) \sum_i a_{3i} \mathbf{e}_i$. For a certain $I = i_1 i_2$,

$$\mathbf{e}_I \mathbf{e}_i = \mathbf{e}_{i_1} \mathbf{e}_{i_2} \mathbf{e}_i = \begin{cases} \mathbf{e}_{i_1} & (i = i_2), \\ -\mathbf{e}_{i_2} & (i = i_1), \\ \mathbf{e}_{i_1 i_2 i} & (i_1 \neq i \neq i_2). \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Therefore $(\mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \mathbf{a}_2) \mathbf{a}_3$ can be separated into a vector, i.e. the sum of terms corresponding to the first two lines of eq. (3), and a 3-blade $\mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \mathbf{a}_2 \wedge \mathbf{a}_3$, i.e. the sum of terms corresponding to the bottom line of (3). A linear combination of 3-blades is called a trivector which can be represented by $\sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}_3} w_I \mathbf{e}_I$, where $\mathcal{I}_3 = \{i_1 i_2 i_3 \mid 1 \leq i_1 < i_2 < i_3 \leq n\}$ is the combinatorial set of three different elements from $\{1, \dots, n\}$.

In the same way the geometric product $\mathbf{a}_1 \dots \mathbf{a}_k$, ($k \leq n$) of linear independent vectors $\mathbf{a}_1, \dots, \mathbf{a}_k$ has as its maximum grade term the k -blade $\mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \mathbf{a}_k$. Linear combinations of k -blades are called k -vectors, represented by $\sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}_k} w_I \mathbf{e}_I$, where $\mathcal{I}_k = \{i_1 \dots i_k \mid 1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n\}$ is the combination set of k elements from $\{1, \dots, n\}$. 1-blades are vectors with $\mathcal{I}_1 = \{i_1 \mid 1 \leq i_1 \leq n\}$. 0-blades are scalars with $\mathcal{I}_0 = \{\emptyset\}$. For the unit real scalar, many authors simply write $\mathbf{e}_\emptyset = 1$. For \mathcal{G}_n , $\bigwedge^k \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the set of all k -blades and \mathcal{G}_n^k denotes set of k -vectors. The relationship between k -blades and k -vectors is $\bigwedge^k \mathbb{R}^n = \{A \in \mathcal{G}_n^k \mid \exists \{\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_k\}, A = \mathbf{b}_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \mathbf{b}_k\}$. The most general element of \mathcal{G}_n is $A = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}} w_I \mathbf{e}_I$, where $\mathcal{I} = \bigcup_{k=0}^n \mathcal{I}_k = \mathcal{P}(\{1, \dots, n\})$, and $\mathcal{P}(\cdot)$ denotes the power set. Concrete examples are the general elements of \mathcal{G}_2 which are linear combinations of $\{1, \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_{12}\}$; and general elements of \mathcal{G}_3 which are linear combinations of $\{1, \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3, \mathbf{e}_{12}, \mathbf{e}_{13}, \mathbf{e}_{23}, \mathbf{e}_{123}\}$. A general element of \mathcal{G}_n can always be represented by $A = \sum_{k=0}^n \langle A \rangle_k$ with $\langle A \rangle_k = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}_k} w_I \mathbf{e}_I$, where $\langle \cdot \rangle_k$ indicates an operator which extracts the k -vector part. The operator that selects the scalar part is abbreviated as $\langle \cdot \rangle = \langle \cdot \rangle_0$.

The geometric product of k ($1 \leq k \leq n$) vectors yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a}_1 &\in \mathcal{G}_n^1 = \mathbb{R}^n = \bigwedge^1 \mathbb{R}^n, \\ \mathbf{a}_1 \mathbf{a}_2 &\in \mathcal{G}_n^0 \oplus \bigwedge^2 \mathbb{R}^n, \\ \mathbf{a}_1 \mathbf{a}_2 \mathbf{a}_3 &\in \mathcal{G}_n^1 \oplus \bigwedge^3 \mathbb{R}^n, \\ &\vdots \\ \mathbf{a}_1 \dots \mathbf{a}_k &\in \begin{cases} \mathcal{G}_n^1 \oplus \dots \oplus \mathcal{G}_n^{k-2} \oplus \bigwedge^k \mathbb{R}^n & (\text{odd } k), \\ \mathcal{G}_n^0 \oplus \dots \oplus \mathcal{G}_n^{k-2} \oplus \bigwedge^k \mathbb{R}^n & (\text{even } k). \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Now we propose a systematic derivation of feature extractions from a set or a series of spatial vectors $\xi = \{\mathbf{p}_l \in \mathbb{R}^n, l = 1, \dots, m\}$. Our method is to extract k -vectors of different grades k ; which encode the variations of the features. Scalars which appeared in eq. (4) in the case of $k = 2$ can also be extracted.

First, assuming ξ is a series of n -dimensional vectors, $n' + 1$ feature extractions are derived where $n' = \min\{n, m\}$. For

$k = 1, \dots, n'$, we write $k' = k - 1$,

$$f_k(\xi) = \{ \langle \mathbf{p}_l \dots \mathbf{p}_{l+k'} \mathbf{e}_I^{-1} \rangle, I \in \mathcal{I}_k, l = 1, \dots, n' - k' \} \in \mathbb{R}^{(m-k')|\mathcal{I}_k|}, \quad (5)$$

where, $|\mathcal{I}_k|$ is the number of combinations of k elements from n elements, and \mathbf{e}_I^{-1} is the inverse of \mathbf{e}_I . For $I = i_1 \dots i_k$, $\mathbf{e}_I^{-1} = \mathbf{e}_{i_k} \dots \mathbf{e}_{i_2} \mathbf{e}_{i_1}$. We further define

$$f_0(\xi) = \{ \langle \mathbf{p}_l \mathbf{p}_{l+1} \rangle, l = 1, \dots, n' - 1 \} \in \mathbb{R}^{m-1}. \quad (6)$$

Next, assuming that ξ is a set of vectors, $n' + 1$ feature extractions can also be derived in the same way

$$f_k(\xi) = \{ \langle \mathbf{p}_{l_1} \dots \mathbf{p}_{l_k} \mathbf{e}_I^{-1} \rangle, I \in \mathcal{I}_k \} \in \mathbb{R}^{(mC_k)|\mathcal{I}_k|}, \quad (7)$$

$$f_0(\xi) = \{ \langle \mathbf{p}_{l_1} \mathbf{p}_{l_2} \rangle \} \in \mathbb{R}^{mC_2}, \quad (8)$$

where mC_k is the number of combinations when we choose k elements from m elements. The dimension of the feature space becomes different from the case where ξ is a series.

Below we show several feature extractions for the case of hand-written digit data of the UCI Repository [13]. Each of the digit data is given by 8 points $\xi = \{\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_8\}$, measured by dividing the hand-written curves in equally long curve segments. A 2-dimensional point is given by $\mathbf{p}_l = x_l \mathbf{e}_1 + y_l \mathbf{e}_2$ with $\sum_{l=1}^8 x_l = \sum_{l=1}^8 y_l = 0$. Using GA, various kinds of feature extraction can be undertaken systematically. Fig. 1 shows some examples of the handwritten digit '1'. They are shown with straight line segments, different from the real curved trajectories of a pen.

Fig. 1. Examples of hand-written digit '1'.

The simplest feature extraction f_1 , which is also used in conventional methods, is

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(\xi) &= [\langle \mathbf{p}_1 \mathbf{e}_1^{-1} \rangle, \langle \mathbf{p}_1 \mathbf{e}_2^{-1} \rangle, \dots, \langle \mathbf{p}_8 \mathbf{e}_1^{-1} \rangle, \langle \mathbf{p}_8 \mathbf{e}_2^{-1} \rangle] \\ &= [\mathbf{p}_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{p}_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{p}_8 \cdot \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{p}_8 \cdot \mathbf{e}_2] \\ &= [x_1, y_1, \dots, x_8, y_8] \in \mathbb{R}^{16}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

A second feature extraction f_2 uses the directed magnitudes of outer products of consecutive points,

$$\begin{aligned} f_2(\xi) &= [\langle \mathbf{p}_1 \mathbf{p}_2 \mathbf{e}_{12}^{-1} \rangle, \dots, \langle \mathbf{p}_7 \mathbf{p}_8 \mathbf{e}_{12}^{-1} \rangle] \\ &= [x_1 y_2 - x_2 y_1, \dots, x_7 y_8 - x_8 y_7] \in \mathbb{R}^7. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

A third feature extraction f_0 uses the inner product of consecutive points

$$\begin{aligned} f_0(\xi) &= [\langle \mathbf{p}_1 \mathbf{p}_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle \mathbf{p}_7 \mathbf{p}_8 \rangle] \\ &= [x_1 x_2 + y_1 y_2, \dots, x_7 x_8 + y_7 y_8] \in \mathbb{R}^7. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

B. Data Distribution Learning for Multi-class Classification

A GMM is useful to approximate a data distribution in a data space. A GMM is characterized by parameters $\Theta = \{\beta_j, \mu_j, \Sigma_j\}$, where β_j , μ_j and Σ_j are the mixture ratio, the mean vector, and the variance covariance matrix of the j -th Gaussian, respectively. The output is

$$p(\xi | \Theta) = \sum_{j=1}^M \beta_j \mathcal{N}_d(f(\xi) - \mu_j; \Sigma_j), \quad (12)$$

where $\mathcal{N}_d(\cdot; \cdot)$ is the d -dimensional Gaussian distribution function whose center is fixed at the origin.

To train M Gaussians with given incomplete data $X = \{x_i = f(\xi_i) \mid 1 \leq i \leq N\}$, the EM algorithm [12] is often utilized. The algorithm identifies both parameters Θ and latent variables $Z = \{z_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \mid 1 \leq j \leq M\}$. The z_{ij} are random variables, which for $z_{ij} = 1$ indicate that the individual datum x_i belongs the j -th of M Gaussian distributions. Thus $\sum_{j=1}^M P(z_{ij}) = 1$. The EM algorithm repeats the E-step and the M-step until $P(Z)$ and Θ converge. The E-step updates the probabilities of Z according to Bayes' theorem $P(Z | X, \Theta) \propto p(X | Z, \Theta)$. The M-step updates the parameters Θ of the Gaussians to maximize the likelihood $l(\Theta, X, Z) = p(X | Z, \Theta)$.

A major drawback of the GMM is its large number of free parameters whose order is $O(Md^2)$. Moreover when the correlation between any pair of features is close to 1, the calculation of the inverse matrix is numerically unstable. So, the GMM becomes unable to compute the correct probability distribution. To remedy this, Tipping and Bishop [14] proposed to use only the eigencomponents with the largest q eigenvalues, where q is a preset value of a Gaussian distribution. But the number of free parameters is not necessarily the same for different Gaussian distributions. With fixed q therefore the GMM produces a bad approximation of a probability distribution. To improve this, Meinicke and Ritter [15] proposed to use only the eigencomponents of Gaussian distributions which are larger than a certain cutoff. The cutoff eigenvalue is set at $\lambda_- = \alpha \lambda_{\max}$, where $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ is a hyper parameter and λ_{\max} is the largest eigenvalue of the variance covariance matrix of incomplete data X . It means

Fig. 2. Flow of multi-class classification. The top diagram shows the training of the GMM for class $C \in \{‘0’, \dots, ‘9’\}$. The D_{1C} denotes a subset of training samples whose label is C . The $f : \xi \mapsto x$ shows feature extraction. Either of $\{f_1, f_2, f_0\}$ is chosen as f . The bottom diagram shows estimation by the learned GMMs. The same f chosen for training is used here. The GMM_C outputs $p(\xi | C)$. The final estimation is $C^* = \arg \max_C p(\xi | C) P(C)$, where $P(C)$ is the prior distribution. The set D_3 consists of independent test data.

that we develop eq. (12)

$$\begin{aligned} p(x | \Theta) &= \sum_{j=1}^M \beta_j \prod_{k=1}^d \mathcal{N}_1((x - \mu_j) \cdot v_k; \lambda_k) \\ &\approx \sum_{j=1}^M \beta_j \left\{ \prod_{k=1}^{q_j} \mathcal{N}_1((x - \mu_j) \cdot v_k; \lambda_k) \right\} \\ &\quad \times \left\{ \mathcal{N}_1\left((x - \mu_j)_-; \lambda_- \right) \right\}^{d - q_j}, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where, λ_k is the k -th largest eigenvalue of the j -th Gaussian distribution. The v_k is the corresponding eigenvector. Because $k \leq q_j \Leftrightarrow \lambda_k > \lambda_-$, the bracket $(x - \mu_j)_-$ is the length of the component, which is perpendicular to the q_j eigenvectors with the largest eigenvalues.

The flow of training and estimation of hand-written digit classification, as an example of multi-class classification, is shown in Fig. 2. The M and α for each GMM are decided by validation with dataset D_2 .

C. Mixture of Experts

Each feature extraction derived with GA has advantages and disadvantages. A big merit of adopting learning of distributions rather than learning of input-output relations is that the learned distributions allow us to obtain reliable inference by mixing plural weak learners. In this study, we therefore use a mixture of GMMs. Inferences are mixed as

$$p(\xi | C) = \prod_{k=0}^2 p(f_k(\xi) | C). \quad (14)$$

Fig. 3 shows the mixture of different GMMs. Inferences via different feature extractions are mixed to produce the output $p(\xi | C)$.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Classification of Hand-written Digits

We used the Pen-Based Recognition of Hand-written Digits dataset (Pendigits dataset in the following) of the UCI Repository [13] as an example application for multi-class

Fig. 3. Mixture of GMMs. Three GMMs via different feature extractions are mixed to yield output $p(\xi | C)$.

classification because digits have two-dimensional spatial features. The Pendigits dataset consists of 10992 samples written by 44 people. Among these samples 7494 samples were written by 30 people, divided into learning data D_1 , and validation data D_2 . The 3498 remaining samples were written by 14 other people and are used as test data D_3 . In the sample collection, the pen point coordinates at 100 msec intervals were measured on a tablet with a resolution of 500×500 pixels. Eight points $\{r_l\}$ dividing the orbit of the pen point into 7 equally long segments were chosen, and scaled so that both the horizontal and vertical ranges became $[0, 100]$. The aspect ratio changes when scaling, and thus some original geometric information is lost. But we do not investigate the influence of changing these aspect ratios in this paper. In this study, we carry out the feature extraction with GA, after computing $\mathbf{p}_l = \mathbf{r}_l - \bar{\mathbf{r}}$, i.e. setting the origin $\bar{\mathbf{r}}$ at the center of the digit.

B. Classification Result of Each Feature Extraction and Mixture of Experts

For each feature extraction $f \in \{f_1, f_2, f_0\}$, the GMM learned from D_1 with 4 values of $\alpha \in \{0.1, 0.01, 0.001, 0.0001\}$ and we then evaluated the correct classification rate for D_2 . Table I shows the results. In Table I, the maximal classification rate is underlined. $\alpha = 0.01$ was therefore chosen for all feature extractions $\{f_1, f_2, f_0\}$.

TABLE I
CORRECT CLASSIFICATION RATE FOR D_2 FOR VARIOUS α .

α	f_1	f_2	f_0
0.1	93.22%	95.09%	84.08%
0.01	<u>99.36%</u>	<u>96.53%</u>	<u>90.13%</u>
0.001	99.28%	96.43%	89.44%
0.0001	98.88%	96.45%	89.78%

Table II shows the results of the identified models M , with $\bar{q} = \frac{\sum_j q_j}{M}$ and the number of misclassifications via coordinates f_1 . In Table II, e.g. the cell of column '0' and row '8' shows 11 samples of '0' data which were misclassified to '8'. The total number of misclassifications was 100 and the correct classification rate was 97.14%. Table III shows the results of the identified models and the number of misclassifications via outer products f_2 . The total number of misclassifications was 201 and the correct classification rate was 94.25%. Table IV shows the results of the identified models and the number of misclassifications

via inner products f_0 . The total number of misclassifications was 494 and the correct classification rate was 85.88%.

TABLE II
IDENTIFIED MODELS AND NUMBER OF MISCLASSIFICATIONS VIA COORDINATES f_1 .

	'0'	'1'	'2'	'3'	'4'	'5'	'6'	'7'	'8'	'9'
M	6	7	5	5	5	8	7	6	8	9
\bar{q}	6	6.1	8.4	9.4	8.4	3	6.4	7.8	7.5	8.7
'0'	–						1		11	
'1'		–	3							
'2'		2	–					1		
'3'		1		–		1		2		1
'4'					–	10				1
'5'				2		–				4
'6'						2	–		2	
'7'		32		3				–	3	
'8'						1			–	
'9'		3				10		3	1	–

TABLE III
IDENTIFIED MODELS AND NUMBER OF MISCLASSIFICATIONS VIA OUTER PRODUCTS f_2 .

	'0'	'1'	'2'	'3'	'4'	'5'	'6'	'7'	'8'	'9'
M	2	7	3	3	3	4	3	6	7	8
\bar{q}	7	4.2	5.3	6	7	4.7	5.3	5.5	5.1	5.5
'0'	–									
'1'		–	9	2	6			10		1
'2'		5	–					1	1	
'3'		5		–		1				1
'4'					–		3		2	9
'5'		1		4	15	–			1	17
'6'	1				4		–		1	11
'7'		30	6	2				–	4	7
'8'									–	2
'9'		1		5		23		9	6	–

Tables II, III, IV, clearly show the differences in the misclassifications by the different feature extractions. Because the feature extraction f_1 keeps the coordinate information of each point, it results in a smaller number of misclassifications. But it has other disadvantages. For example, because the first point \mathbf{p}_1 of most learning data of '0' is in the top left area, some test data whose \mathbf{p}_1 is in the top right area, are misclassified. The feature extractions f_2 and f_0 , on the other hand, lose the coordinate information of each point. But they extract partial shape features not affected by the position of the part of the digit under concern. Therefore f_2 and f_0 correctly classified the '0' data with curves beginning in the top right area. Therefore, a mixture of different f_1, f_2, f_0 expert feature extractions works best.

Table V shows the number of misclassifications using a mixture of experts. The total number of misclassifications was 75 and the correct classification rate was 97.86%, both better than the result of only using f_1, f_2 or f_0 .

TABLE IV

IDENTIFIED MODELS AND NUMBER OF MISCLASSIFICATIONS VIA INNER PRODUCTS f_0 .

	'0'	'1'	'2'	'3'	'4'	'5'	'6'	'7'	'8'	'9'
M	2	8	9	4	4	8	6	6	5	5
\bar{q}	6.5	4.9	4.8	6.3	6	5.1	5.3	4.8	6.6	6.8
'0'	-							1		1
'1'		-	9	2	7	5		1	9	4
'2'	1	13	-	15	16	9		2		1
'3'		8	8	-	4	5			1	5
'4'		12	35	3	-	5		4	11	9
'5'	5	6	4	29	1	-		3	10	23
'6'	5	6	1		4		-	8	4	5
'7'		16	4	2	12		20	-	19	3
'8'	2	3			7	13	2	14	-	2
'9'	1	30	1	1	4	14		1	3	-

TABLE V

NUMBER OF MISCLASSIFICATIONS BY MIXTURE OF EXPERTS.

	'0'	'1'	'2'	'3'	'4'	'5'	'6'	'7'	'8'	'9'
'0'	-								6	
'1'		-	4							
'2'		4	-							
'3'		2		-		1				
'4'					-	3				
'5'				4		-				3
'6'							-		4	
'7'		28		4				-	2	1
'8'									-	
'9'		3				2		3	1	-

C. The Robustness Against Measurement Environment Fluctuation

We assumed cases of different measurement environments from the one in which both D_1 and D_2 have been measured. We generated a dataset $D'_3 = \{R(\xi, \varphi), \xi \in D_3, \varphi \sim \mathcal{U}(\varepsilon)\}$ that randomly rotated each digit of the test data D_3 . $\mathcal{U}(\varepsilon)$ is a uniform distribution of $[-\varepsilon, \varepsilon]$ and φ is a random variable. We generated 20 different sets D'_3 from the test dataset D_3 for each $\varepsilon \in \{\frac{\pi}{40}, \frac{\pi}{20}, \frac{\pi}{10}\}$ and classified them. $R(\xi, \theta)$ rotates all the points of ξ by θ . Fig. 4 shows the average and the standard deviation of the correct classification rate when using the feature extraction f_1 and the mixture of experts.

The classification precision using only feature extraction f_1 decreased remarkably with increasing ε . On the other hand, the classification precision using the mixture of expert did not decrease that much. The rotations had no influence in the cases of f_2 and f_0 .

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, we proposed systematic feature extraction methods by using GA. To the extracted features, we applied the classification of the hand-written digits by using GMMs. We applied the proposed method to two-dimensional objects of hand-written digits deriving 3 ways of feature extraction, via coordinates, outer products, and inner products. The classification success rate using coordinate value feature

Fig. 4. Correct classification rate with f_1 and mixture of experts.

extraction was higher than only using outer product feature extraction or inner product feature extraction. However, when we assumed cases of different measurement environments, the classification success rate by pure coordinate value feature extraction dropped substantially for rotated test data. In contrast to this, with the mixture of experts, the classification success rate was not only higher in the case of a constant measurement environment, it was also much more stable in the case of large rotations of the test data. Therefore, we can confirm that the strategy to mix different GA feature extractions is superior in both classification precision and robustness when compared with pure coordinate value features, which is the most often used conventional method.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by Grant-in-Aid for the 21st century COE program "Frontiers of Computational Science" Nagoya University and Grant-in-Aid for Young Scientists (B) #19700218.

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Proceedings of IEEE World Congress on Computational Intelligence, Hong Kong, June 1-6, 2008.